

Open Materials for Retrorsine Impairs Liver Regeneration by Inducing Progenitor Cell-Senescence via ROS after Partial Hepatectomy

Yan Cui^{1,2,3,4}, Li Li^{1,3,4}, Yu He^{1,3,4}, Shan Shan^{1,3}, Lin Liu^{1,3}, Jiangbo Ren^{1,3}, Hui Wang^{1,3},
Miaoran Yang^{1,3}, Xinyan Zhao^{1,3}, Jidong Jia^{1,3,*}, and Ping Wang^{1,3,*}

¹ Liver Research Center, Beijing Friendship Hospital, Capital Medical University, Beijing 100050, China

² Institutional Office, Beijing Friendship Hospital, Capital Medical University, Beijing 100050, China

³ State Key Laboratory of Digestive Health and National Clinical Research Center for Digestive Diseases, Beijing 10069, China.

⁴ These authors contributed equally: Cui Yan, Li Li and Yu He

1. Retrorsine (10mg/mL) for mouse experiments

- (1) The reagent was freshly prepared before use.
- (2) Distilled water (0.5 mL) was added to Retrorsine (10 mg, Yuan Ye Biol, Shanghai, China).
- (3) 125 μ L 1 N HCl was added to the Retrorsine solution drop by drop to dissolve Retrorsine with final pH 2.5.
- (4) The solution was neutralized to pH 7.0 with 4 μ L 1 N NaOH.
- (5) 75 μ L 2mol/L NaCl and 300 μ L distilled water was added to the solution with a final concentration of 10 mg/mL Retrorsine and 150 mmol/L NaCl.

2. Tamoxifen (1.6mg/mL) for mouse experiments

- (1) The reagent was freshly prepared before use.
- (2) 10mL corn oil (Macklin, Shanghai, China) was added to 16mg Tamoxifen (Macklin).
- (3) Mix thoroughly on an orbital shaker (Kylin-Bell Lab Instruments, Haimen, Jiangsu Province, China) at room temperature for 2 hours.

3. Partial Hepatectomy for mouse experiments

- (1) The entire surgical procedure was performed under aseptic conditions in a laminar flow cabinet (Bo Xun, Shanghai, China).
- (2) The mice were anesthetized with pentobarbital sodium (40mg/kg B.W.) i.p., and ophthalmic ointment was applied to both eyes to prevent corneal drying during anesthesia.
- (3) The abdominal fur was shaved with an electric clipper.
- (4) The exposed skin was disinfected with three alternating washes of povidone-iodine and 70%

ethanol.

- (5) A subcostal incision (approximately 1.5~2 cm in length) was made through the skin and the muscle to allow for the complete exposure of the liver.
- (6) The left lateral lobe was lifted with cotton-tipped sticks, and a suture loop was placed around it and hand-tied.
- (7) The parenchymal resection was performed about 2 mm distal to the ligature to prevent suture slippage.
- (8) Then, the right medial lobe was lifted with cotton-tipped sticks, and a suture loop was placed around it leaving the gallbladder intact and hand-tied.
- (9) The parenchymal resection was performed about 2 mm distal to the ligature to prevent suture slippage.
- (10) After resection, a bright red color in the residual parenchyma confirmed the preservation of its blood supply and venous drainage.
- (11) The serosal surfaces of the abdominal viscera were gently blotted dry with sterile gauze to remove residual blood.
- (12) The abdominal incision was closed by suturing the muscle and skin layers separately.
- (13) After the procedure, the mice were placed on a warming blanket to prevent hypothermia and were maintained until they regained full ambulatory capacity.

4. Organoid Primary Culture *in vitro*

- (1) Hepatic progenitor organoids were prepared by a tissue dissociation kit (CELLada Biotechnology, Beijing, China) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

- (2) The male C57BL/6J mice were anesthetized with pentobarbital sodium (40mg/kg B.W., i.p.), and the abdominal fur was shaved with an electric clipper.
- (3) The exposed skin was disinfected with three alternating washes of povidone-iodine and 70% ethanol.
- (4) A subcostal incision (approximately 1.5-2 cm in length) was made through the skin and muscle to allow for the complete exposure of the liver.
- (5) Following thoracotomy, an incision was made in the right atrium.
- (6) The liver was then perfused *via* the left ventricle with saline to remove blood cells from the hepatic vasculature until the liver changed to a uniform pale color.
- (7) The liver was carefully excised, transferred to a dish containing PBS, and gently rinsed to clean the surface.
- (8) The liver was transferred to a PBS-filled Petri dish and minced into small fragments to facilitate subsequent enzymatic digestion.
- (9) The liver fragments were transferred to a new 15ml centrifuge tube and resuspended with an appropriate volume of tissue dissociation reagent at a 1:4 (tissue vol : solution vol) ratio.
- (10) The mixture was gently triturated using a 1 mL pipette tip.
- (11) The digestion mixture was incubated in a 37°C and 5% CO₂ incubator (Heracell 240i, ThermoFisher Scientific) for 30 minutes. During the incubation, the tissue was gently triturated every 5 minutes using a 1 mL pipette tip to enhance dissociation.
- (12) An equal volume of PBS was added to terminate the enzymatic digestion.
- (13) The digested cells were filtered through a 100 µm cell strainer into a new 15ml centrifuge tube and washed with PBS at 1200 g and 4 °C for 5min (Sorvall ST16R, ThermoFisher

Scientific).

- (14) The supernatant was discarded, and the cell pellet was suspended in ice-cold DMEM/F12 medium and incubated on ice for 5 minutes.
- (15) The cell suspension was mixed with equal volume of Matrigel Basement Membrane Matrix (Corning), and 25 μ L cell-Matrigel mixture per well was plated in 24-well plate.
- (16) The 24-well plate was placed in a 37°C and 5% CO₂ incubator (Heracell 240i, ThermoFisher Scientific) for 30 minutes.
- (17) After Matrigel polymerization, 600 μ L normal mouse liver tissue organoid culture medium (CELLada Biotechnology) per well was added carefully and cultured at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ (Heracell 240i, ThermoFisher Scientific).
- (18) The medium was changed every 2 days, and the organoids were passaged after 6 days.

5. Organoid Passage *in vitro*

- (1) The culture medium was discarded, and the Matrigel aliquot was dissociated into a homogeneous suspension by gently pipetting with 1 mL of ice-cold PBS.
- (2) The organoids and Matrigel mixture were transferred into a new 15mL centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 1300rpm for 5 min (Sorvall ST16R, ThermoFisher Scientific).
- (3) The supernatant was discarded, and 400 μ L 0.25% Trypsin-0.02% EDTA was added to the pellet and resuspended gently.
- (4) The mixture was gently triturated every 5 minutes using a 200 μ L pipette tip to enhance dissociation.
- (5) The digestion process was monitored under a microscope (Ts2 FL, Nikon, Japan). Once the

organoids had dissociated into single cells, an equal volume of complete medium was added to neutralize the trypsin.

- (6) The mixture was resuspended with 4 mL PBS and centrifuged at 1300rpm for 5 min (Sorvall ST16R, ThermoFisher Scientific).
- (7) The supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was suspended in ice-cold DMEM/F12 medium and incubated on ice for 5 minutes.
- (8) The cell suspension was mixed with equal volume of Matrigel Basement Membrane Matrix (Corning), and 25 μ L cell-Matrigel mixture per well was plated in 24-well plate.
- (9) The 24-well plate was placed in a 37°C and 5% CO₂ incubator (Heracell 240i, ThermoFisher Scientific) for 30 minutes.
- (10) After Matrigel polymerization, 600 μ L normal mouse liver tissue organoid culture medium (CELLada Biotechnology) per well was added carefully and cultured at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ (Heracell 240i, ThermoFisher Scientific).